

Nitro-derivatives of Dibenzylaniline.

BY RANCHHODJI DAJIBHAI DESAI.

Matzduira (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1611) prepared *p*-nitrodibenzylaniline by the nitration of dibenzylaniline with fuming nitric acid ($d=1.52$), while by using excess of the same acid, Pinnow and Wiskow (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 913) obtained 2:4-dinitrodibenzylaniline. It has now been found that under the same conditions, if nitric acid of $d 1.48$ is used besides the above nitro compounds, very small amounts of *o*-nitrodibenzylaniline and 2:6-dinitro-dibenzylaniline respectively are also formed.

The three nitro-dibenzylanilines (*ortho*, *meta*, and *para*-isomers) can be reduced to the corresponding amino derivatives by zinc dust and hydrochloric acid in alcoholic solution, although the *o*-nitro-derivative presents some difficulties. The action of benzaldehyde was studied on *p*- and *m*-amino-dibenzylaniline. From the former, Matzduira (*loc. cit.*) claims to have isolated a compound melting at 130° , and having the constitution (*p*) $(C_7H_7)_2N \cdot C_6H_4NH \cdot CH(OH) \cdot C_6H_5$. Repeating Matzduira's experiments with scrupulous details, a compound melting at $166-167^{\circ}$ was obtained. This proved to be the Schiff's base *p*) $(C_7H_7)_2N \cdot C_6H_4N=CH \cdot C_6H_5$ from the following considerations:—

(1) Estimation of nitrogen, as well as the analysis of the hydrochloride points to the formula $C_{27}H_{29}N_3$ for the base.

(2) The substance is recovered unchanged after heating with phosphorus pentoxide in xylene solution.

(3) The chloroform solution of the base adds up bromine at 0° giving the dibromide. According to Hantzsch (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 2773), and James and Judd (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1427), Schiff's bases form dibromides.

From similar considerations, the compounds formed by the action of benzaldehyde on *p*-benzylaminoaniline and *m*-amino-dibenzylaniline are true Schiff's bases and not amino-carbinols.

EXPERIMENTAL.

p-Nitrodibenzylaniline.—To a solution of dibenzylaniline (10 gm.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) cooled to 5°, 3 c.c. of nitric acid ($d=1.48$) diluted with 25 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were slowly added. Mechanical stirring was used throughout, and the temperature of the solution was not allowed to rise above 10°. After two hours, some *p*-nitrodibenzylaniline that separated out was filtered off, and the solution diluted with water when the nitro compound separated out (yield, 10.5 gm.). The crude product was crystallised from boiling glacial acetic acid, when yellow plates melting at 132-133° were obtained. After removing the solvent, the residue was treated with alcohol. The *p*-nitro-derivative did not go into solution, while the *ortho* compound was left as an oil after removing alcohol completely. Yield of pure *p*-nitro compound=9.5 gm. while that of the *ortho*-derivative is 1 gm.

Synthesis from p-Nitraniline and Benzyl Chloride.—A mixture of *p*-nitraniline (14 gm.), benzyl chloride (26 gm.), anhydrous sodium acetate (18 gm.) and iodine (0.2 gm.) was heated on a sand-bath for 12 hours. The mixture was poured into water, and the solid was filtered off. The crude mass was purified by digesting it with xylene (50 c.c.) which removed unaltered *p*-nitraniline and *p*-nitrobenzylaniline. The residue was pure *p*-nitrodibenzylaniline (yield, 65 per cent.).

p-Nitrodibenzylaniline dissolves readily in benzene and acetone, fairly easily in hot glacial acetic acid, less readily in cold glacial acetic acid, and hot alcohol, and is almost insoluble in cold alcohol. It does not form a hydrochloride. It is easily reduced to the corresponding amino compound by zinc dust and hydrochloric acid in alcoholic solution. On dilution with water, the zinc double salt separates out in white needles melting at 200-202°. The base can be liberated by decomposing the salt with alkali. It crystallises from ether in white needles melting at 89-90°, but readily turns brown in air.

The *acetyl derivative* crystallises from alcohol in white plates melting at 137-138°. (Found: N, 8.62. $C_{17}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 8.48 per cent.) The *benzoyl derivative* crystallises from glacial acetic acid in white, pointed needles melting at 166°. (Found: N, 7.21. $C_{27}H_{24}ON_2$ requires N, 7.14 per cent.).

Benzylidene-p-dibenzylaminoaniline, $C_6H_5CH=NC_6H_4N(C_6H_5)_2$ (p).—This is prepared by dissolving the amino compound (1.5 g.) in benzaldehyde (1.5 g.) at 0° . The mixture is washed with alcohol, and the yellow, microcrystalline powder that is obtained is crystallised from benzene when microcrystalline needles melting at $166-167^\circ$ are obtained. This is readily soluble in chloroform, acetone and glacial acetic acid. Warming with dilute HCl decomposes it into its components. It remains unaffected when heated with phosphorus pentoxide in xylene solution. When heated with acetic anhydride, it gives the acetyl derivative of *p*-aminodibenzylaniline, m.p. $137-138^\circ$. (Found: N, 7.52. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2$ requires N, 7.45 per cent.). The *hydrochloride* of the base is prepared by passing HCl into a benzene solution of the base. White plates are obtained when recrystallised from glacial acetic acid. It does not show any definite signs of melting, but sublimes on the sides of the capillary. At about 190° , it turns yellow, but reverts to the original colour on cooling. The hydrochloride is decomposed by hot water. (Found: Cl, 8.72, $C_8H_8N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 8.6 per cent.).

The *di-bromide* is prepared by treating the chloroform solution of the base with bromine in chloroform at 0° . It is a pale-yellow powder soluble in chloroform, benzene and alcohol and melts at $220-225^\circ$ with decomposition. Heating with alcoholic NaOH decomposes it into benzaldehyde and a product containing bromine. (Found: Br, 29.9. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2Br_2$ requires Br, 29.8 per cent.). *Synthesis of p-Nitrobenzylaniline*.—This was prepared by heating a mixture of *p*-nitraniline (14 g.), benzyl chloride (13 g.), and anhydrous sodium acetate (9 g.) and 0.2 gm. of iodine in an oil-bath at $125-130^\circ$ for 8 hours. The mass was poured into water and the solid was filtered off. When crystallised from toluene, tiny, golden-yellow, prismatic needles melting at 147° were obtained. It is easily soluble in benzene, acetone, glacial acetic acid, and ether. The alcoholic solution is easily reduced to the corresponding amino-compound by zinc dust and HCl. The resulting base is an oil, turning brown in air.

The *acetyl derivative* crystallises from alcohol in silky needles melting at $141-142^\circ$. (Found: N, 11.9. $C_{15}H_{15}ON_2$ requires N, 11.66 per cent.).

The *benzoyl derivative* crystallises from glacial acetic acid in white plates melting at $182-183^\circ$. (Found: N, 9.47. $C_{16}H_{15}ON_2$ requires N, 9.27 per cent.).

Benzylidene-p-benzylaminoaniline.

This was prepared by adding 2 g. of the base to 2 g. of benzaldehyde at 0°. After one hour, the mixture was washed with light petrol, and the solid was crystallised from alcohol when pale yellow plates melting at 92-93° were obtained. On heating with dilute HCl, it is decomposed into its components. (Found: N, 10.0. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$ requires N, 9.8 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* prepared by the usual method crystallises from glacial acetic acid in stout, white needles, melting at 170-172°, and is readily decomposed by water. (Found: Cl, 10.86. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2$ HCl requires Cl, 10.97 per cent.).

The *dibromide* prepared as above is a yellow, micro-crystalline powder, soluble in chloroform, alcohol, benzene and carbon tetrachloride. It sinters at 200°, and melts at 210° with decomposition. Warm alcoholic KOH decomposes it into benzaldehyde and a brominated compound. (Found: Br, 35.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{Br}_2$ requires Br, 35.9 per cent.).

Synthesis of o-Nitrodibenzylaniline.

A mixture of *o*-nitraniline (13.8 g.), benzyl chloride (40 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (17 g.) and iodine (0.2 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 15 hours. The mixture was steam-distilled to remove excess of benzyl chloride. The residue was extracted with ether, the solution dehydrated with anhydrous sodium sulphate, and ether distilled off. The residue was distilled under reduced pressure, when almost the whole of it distilled away leaving a slight residue of *o*-nitraniline. (yield 20 gms). The distillate solidified when kept in a freezing mixture. It crystallises from light petroleum in yellow plates melting at 32-33°. It is easily soluble in alcohol, acetic acid, acetone, benzene and petroleum. It does not form a hydrochloride. It can be reduced to the corresponding amino compound by zinc dust and HCl, though with difficulty. The resulting base is an oil darkening in air.

The *acetyl derivative* crystallises from alcohol in white needles melting at 121-122°. (Found: N, 8.6. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{19}\text{ON}$ requires N, 8.48 per cent.).

The *benzoyl derivative* crystallises from glacial acetic acid in white, prismatic needles melting at 155-156°. (Found: N, 7.2. $C_{17}H_{15}ON$, requires N, 7.14 per cent.).

Synthesis of m-Nitrodibenzylaniline.

A mixture of *m*-nitraniline (14 g.), benzyl chloride (26 g.), anhydrous sodium acetate (18 g.), and iodine (0.2 g.) was heated at 125-130° for five hours. The product was poured into water, and the oily mass was extracted with ether. The residue did not solidify on keeping in a desiccator, hence concentrated HCl was added. The hydrochloride which separated as a solid was filtered off, and the free base was obtained in a solid condition by decomposing it with NaOH solution (yield, 25 gm.).

The base is soluble in ether, benzene, acetone, toluene, and alcohol. From the latter solvent, it crystallises out in golden-yellow, silky needles melting at 73-74°. (Found: N, 8.88. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2$, requires N, 8.8 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallises from glacial acetic acid in white prismatic needles, melting at 140-142°. It loses HCl on keeping in a desiccator, and is rapidly decomposed by water. (Found: Cl, 10.1. $C_{16}H_{13}O_2N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 10.0 per cent.).

m-Aminodibenzylaniline was obtained by reducing the nitro compound with zinc dust and HCl. The free base is an oil which is oxidised by air.

The *acetyl derivative* crystallises from alcohol in white, slender needles melting at 143-144°.

The *benzoyl derivative* crystallises from glacial acetic acid in prismatic needles melting at 171-172°. (Found: N, 7.25. $C_{17}H_{15}ON$, requires N, 7.14 per cent.).

Benzylidene-m-dibenzylaminoaniline.

This was prepared by adding 1.5 gm. of the base to 1.5 gm. of benzaldehyde at 0°. After washing the mixture with dilute alcohol, the yellow solid was crystallised from benzene when yellow, microscopic plates, m. p. 156-158° were obtained. It is decomposed into its components by warm, dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found: N, 7.55. $C_{17}H_{15}N_2$, requires N, 7.45 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* prepared as usual melts at 195° with decomposition. It is easily decomposed by water, (Found: Cl, 8·7. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2$, HCl requires Cl, 8·6 per cent.).

The *dibromide* was prepared as usual. It is a yellow powder melting at 196-198° with decomposition. (Found: Br, 30·0. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2$, Br₂ requires Br, 29·8 per cent.).

2:4-Dinitro-dibenzylaniline and 2:6-Dinitro-dibenzylaniline.

To a solution of dibenzylaniline (10 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 c.c.) 10 c.c. of nitric acid (d 1·48) diluted with 25 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were slowly added. Mechanical stirring was kept throughout, and the temperature was kept at 15-20°. After nearly three hours, lemon-yellow prismatic needles began to separate. After filtering off the solid, the solution was freely diluted with water when the nitro compound separated as a yellow powder (yield, 11·0 gm.). The crude mass was dissolved in 50 c.c. of boiling glacial acetic acid, and on cooling, pure crystals of 2:4-dinitrodibenzylaniline were obtained. This substance melts at 103-104° and not at 106° as given by Pinnow and Wiskow (*loc. cit.*). On concentrating the mother-liquor, a further amount of the same product was obtained. The mother-liquor was reduced to one-third of its original bulk. Spontaneous crystallisation gave two types of crystals, *viz.* lemon-yellow, prismatic needles and orange-yellow, stout, pointed, prismatic needles. The latter were mechanically separated by forceps, and melted at 107°. This is the new nitro derivative which has been shown to be 2:6-dinitro-dibenzylaniline. The yield of this compound is very small (0·5 gm.).

2:4-Dinitro-dibenzylaniline is sparingly soluble in ether, but readily in hot glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 11·78. $C_{16}H_{11}O_4N_2$, requires N, 11·57 per cent.).

Decomposition of 2:4-Dinitrodibenzylaniline.

One gm. of the compound was heated with 5 c.c. of acetic anhydride and 1 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for two hours under reflux. On pouring the mixture into water, a yellow powder was obtained, and the filtrate smelt of benzyl chloride. Recrystallisation of the crude product from glacial acetic acid gave fine yellow needles melting at 116°. (Found: N, 15·5. $C_{15}H_{11}O_4N_2$, requires N, 15·4 per cent.). This is 2:4-dinitrodibenzylaniline synthesised by Mulder (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1906, 26, 108).

In another experiment, the heating of the above mixture was carried out in a sealed tube at 145-150° for 8 hours. A heavy oil settled at the bottom when the mixture was poured into water. This was removed by extraction with ether, and then acetylated as usual. The solid, on crystallisation from alcohol, gave pale-white needles melting at 120°. This is the acetyl derivative of 2:4-dinitraniline (Rudnew, *Zeit. Chem.*, 1871, 202). (Found: N, 18·8. $C_8H_7O_2N_2$, requires N, 18·66 per cent.).

2:6-Dinitro-dibenzylaniline.

The method of isolating this substance has already been described. It dissolves easily in acetic acid, acetone and benzene, but sparingly in alcohol. It melts at 107°, and when mixed with 2:4-dinitro-dibenzylaniline, the m.p. is lowered to 85-90°. (Found: N, 11·68. $C_{20}H_{17}O_4N_2$, requires N, 11·57 per cent.).

Decomposition of 2:6-Dinitro-dibenzylaniline.

0·3 Gm. was heated with 3 c.c. of acetic anhydride and 1 c.c. of conc. HCl for two hours, under reflux. When the mixture was poured into water, a strong smell of benzyl chloride was perceptible, and a solid was obtained. When crystallised from alcohol, yellow needles melting at 138° were obtained. This gave all the tests for 2:6-dinitraniline (Hoff, *Annalen*, 1900 311, 108; Salkowsky, *ibid*, 1874 174, 237). (Found: N, 23·1. $C_8H_6O_4N_2$, requires N, 22·95 per cent.).

This reaction establishes the constitution of the original dinitro compound melting at 107° as 2:6-dinitrophenyldibenzylamine (2:6) $(NO_2)_2C_6H_3N(C_2H_5)_2$ (1).

The work described in this communication was carried out at the Royal Institute of Science, Bombay, and the author takes this opportunity of expressing his thanks to Dr. A. N. Meldrum for his sympathy and encouragement, and for giving full access to the resources of the laboratory.

